

LEVERAGING EFFECTIVE PUBLIC RELATIONS STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING GOVERNANCE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN 21ST-CENTURY NIGERIA

Eke, Chigozi (PhD). and Naanee, Barivule Vivian.

Department of Linguistics and Communication Studies, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

E-mail: chigozi_eke@uniport.edu.ng, naanee_barivule@uniport.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18298773>

Abstract: This study examined the role of effective public relations strategies in enhancing governance and promoting sustainable development in Nigeria. The excellence theory of public relations was anchored in this study. This study adopted a qualitative research methodology, specifically the library research method, to explore the role of public relations in enhancing governance and promoting sustainable development in Nigeria. The population of the study comprised academic literature, government reports, policy documents, books, scholarly articles, and reputable media sources that address public relations practices, governance challenges, and sustainable development initiatives in Nigeria. For the sample size, a purposeful sampling technique was used to select a range of relevant sources, including academic books, journal articles, government publications, and case studies that offer insights into public relations strategies and their impact on governance in Nigeria. A total of 30-40 sources were selected, ensuring diversity and relevance to the study's focus. Data were collected through a systematic review of the selected literature, identifying key themes, patterns, and findings related to the role of public relations in governance. The data were analysed using thematic analysis, allowing for the identification of recurring themes, trends, and insights. The findings revealed that public relations strategies, particularly those based on two-way symmetrical communication, significantly enhance government transparency and accountability by fostering open dialogue between government institutions and citizens, leading to improved public trust. The study concluded that public relations strategies that prioritize two-way symmetrical communication are essential for enhancing government transparency and accountability, as they enable open, honest dialogue between government and citizens, fostering trust and credibility in governance. The study recommended that the Nigerian government should adopt public relations strategies based on two-way communication to enhance transparency and accountability, ensuring regular interaction between government institutions and citizens.

Keywords: Leveraging, Public Relations Strategies, Enhancing Governance, Sustainable Development, 21st-Century Nigeria

Introduction

In the 21st century, effective public relations strategies have emerged as quintessential tools in the enhancement of good governance and fostering sustainable development in Nigeria. The country, being one with diverse cultures, languages, and political dynamics, has peculiar challenges that need effective frameworks of communication for bridging the gaps between governments and citizens (Egwuonwu et al., 2015). Public relations are a channel for clear communication, mutual understanding, and trust-building that underpin effective governance and national development. Public relations comprises strategic communication processes that engender mutually beneficial relationships between organisations and their publics. In the governance context, PR is the purposeful dissemination of information by government entities with the aim to inform, educate, and engage citizens for a knowledgeable citizenry capable of participating actively in democratic processes (Akintola et al., 2023). Such an engagement is very important in a democratic society, since citizens are not only made aware of the policies and initiatives of a government but are also given ways to provide their feedback for promoting accountability and inclusiveness.

The role of public relations in governance in Nigeria has therefore been that of promoting transparency and accountability. In essence, effective PR strategies make the operations of a government less mysterious to the general public through effective communication of government policies, programs, and achievements (Aribisala et al., 2023). This is very key in fighting corruption and building trust with citizens, as it allows them to question the actions taken by a government and holds its officials accountable. For instance, this has improved the extent and the speed of communications by the government through digital platforms in information dissemination, thereby increasing citizens' access to information. Another important public relations function is playing a leading role in image and reputation management for the government. Effective PR strategies in times of crisis or public dissent might help soften the negative perception by disseminating correct information, rectifying misconceptions, and thus showing the government's concern in solving problems (Nwosu, 1990). In this regard, the crisis management aspect of PR is important for safeguarding public confidence and social stability, two major ingredients for sustainable development.

The advent of digital public relations has transformed the landscape of governance in Nigeria. The integration of information and communication technologies into the PR practices has placed a total transformation in the way governments relate to citizens. Digital platforms, including social media, websites, and online forums, have been very instrumental in two-way communication and have made it possible to get real-time dissemination and collection of feedbacks from the target population (Akintola et al., 2023). This digital engagement does not only make the reach of government communications wider, but it also gives way to a more participative form of governance where citizens feel more connected and involved in the decision-making processes. In addition, such public relations strategies are very crucial to encourage socio-political inclusiveness in Nigeria. Through strategic communication, advocacy efforts, and crisis management, PR can help bridge societal divides, amplify the voices

of the marginalized, and build a cohesive national identity (Egwuonwu et al., 2015). This inclusiveness is very important in a country as diverse as Nigeria, as it makes sure that every segment of the population is represented and heard, hence ensuring social harmony and national unity.

The role of public relations in sustainable development is to help give information concerning the development initiatives, policies, and opportunities. PR creates awareness among the public and further involves them in the process by keeping them abreast of developments. This way, the community can participate in the development projects and feel ownership of such projects for their success (Aribisala et al., 2023). Such community involvement is a must for successful and sustainable development programs, since it engenders a feeling of ownership and responsibility among the citizens. Public relations also play a very important part in shaping public attitudes and behaviours toward governmental policies and initiatives. Through strategic communication campaigns, PR can sensitise the citizens on specific policies that bring them a great deal of benefit, working to dispel misconceptions and encourage positive behavioural changes (Otuya-Asohro, 2024). Such influence is particularly important in the implementation of policies that call for public cooperation and support, such as public health initiatives or environmental conservation programs.

Another major factor that also determines the effectiveness of public relations in governance includes the ethical standards upheld by the practitioners. Ethical PR practices ensure that the information being shared with the public is accurate, truthful, and respectful, as it builds a good rapport and credibility (Nwosu, 1990). In this regard, in Nigeria, ethical standards institutionalization is very instrumental in government PR to safeguard against misuse and make sure that the public interest component of PR prevails. The 21st-century challenges of governance and sustainable development in Nigeria will require effective Public Relations strategies. From facilitating transparent communication and promoting engagement with the public to managing the reputation of the government, PR is the elixir that will help solve the complex issues facing the country today (Akintola et al., 2023). The country, in charting its development course, will continue to make the strategic use of public relations one of the cornerstones in building a more inclusive, transparent, and accountable governance framework. This study has become important to show how effective public relations strategies may engender transparency, accountability, and public engagement in the governance of Nigeria, with a view to closing the gap between the government and citizens for better acceptance of policies and working towards national cohesion in a much more digitalised and interconnected world.

Statement of the Problem

While much has been said in achieving sustainable development and ensuring effective governance, some of the perennial challenges that face Nigeria include inadequate communication, lack of transparency, and inadequate public engagement. The governance structure in Nigeria is typified by the divide that separates policymakers from the general public, which causes a lot of misinformation, distrust, and resistance to government-led initiatives. This communication gap has brought about inefficiencies in policy implementation, inadequate service delivery, and lack of accountability, which have further exacerbated the socio-economic challenges of poverty, insecurity,

and political instability in the country. While PR can offer a strategic approach to these challenges by way of mutual understanding and promoting government initiatives, its potential in the Nigerian governance framework remains largely unexploited. This has led to a very limited application of PR strategies, rendering ineffective the communication channels for the government to reach citizens in a meaningful and transparent way.

What is more, the rapidly changing digital environment brings both opportunities and challenges for public relations in governance. On one side, the digital platforms - social media and government websites hold the potential of increasing two-way communication and public participation; on the other hand, their misuse or underutilization is an issue that has contributed to the spread of misinformation and further alienation of the public. Without such well-planned PR programs, it is rather hard for a government to control its image, especially in times of crises or policies that involve scandals. The issue that necessarily becomes pressing under this case is finding a valid PR means by which public gaps in communication may be mended to bridge relations between citizens and government of Nigeria. The study tries to address these concerns by investigating the role that PR strategies play in improving governance and in the creation of a more informed and engaging citizenry.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine public relations practices in relation to government transparency and accountability in Nigeria.
2. To examine the role of public relations in promoting public engagement and trust in government policies.
3. To identify the challenges militating against the effective use of public relations in Nigerian governance and proffer possible solutions.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Public Relations and Its Role in Governance

Public relations is a process of strategic communication that builds mutually beneficial relationships between organizations and their publics (Grunig & Hunt, 1984). In governance, PR acts as a bridge between the government and the public, facilitating the flow of information, nurturing transparency, and building public trust. According to Cutlip et al. (2013), good PR practices in governance include strategic management of communication, where the general public comes to understand and accept government policies, programs, and initiatives. This may adopt a multi-channel approach, including press releases, public briefings, and using other digital platforms to engage citizens and other stakeholders effectively.

Transparency and accountability are the backbones of good governance, and public relations go a long way in ensuring these ideals are met. Governments that embrace PR strategies are better placed to inform the public of their activities, clear up misconceptions, and update the public regularly on policy implementation (Macnamara, 2016). In Nigeria, where problems of governance challenges, such as corruption and misinformation, are widespread, PR can help in the recreation of public confidence because it assures open and honest communication between government institutions and citizens (Ogbondah, 2017). Effective PR strategies can also encourage civic

participation in citizens' efforts to contribute to policy-making processes and hold their leaders accountable. Additionally, public relations facilitate crisis management within governance structures.

Public backlash caused by supposed bureaucratic inefficiencies, policy failures, or other forms of crisis brought about by either economic downturn or security challenges must be countered. According to Coombs (2019), proactive crisis communication via PR helps to monitor public perception. In Nigeria, the timing of communication during periods of health crises or any issue of national security can either win or lose them public response or cooperation, say Ezeah 2020. In sum, the PR professionals must adapt strategic crisis communication models that address public concern, provide information, and reassure citizens of the efforts by the government. The emergence of digital media has enlarged the scope of public relations in governance. Social media platforms, websites, and mobile applications have now become indispensable tools for governments to interact with the public in real-time (Kent & Taylor, 2016).

The deployment of digital PR strategies gives the ability to increase participatory governance by using interactive communication and feedback mechanisms in Nigeria. However, this is largely obstructed by the spread of false information and a lack of digital literacy levels among citizens (Adegbola, 2021). This means that Nigerian policymakers have to invest in programs for digital literacy and ethical public relations to harvest the great dividends that come with modern communication technologies in governance.

Public Relations Strategies for Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is defined as meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (United Nations, 1987). Public relations can play a critical role in advancing sustainable development by creating awareness, mobilizing public support, and facilitating collaboration among diverse stakeholders (Grunig & Dozier, 2002). In Nigeria, PR will aid in the advocacy of environmental conservation, social equity, and economic growth by communicating effectively on the need for sustainable development initiatives. Strategic PR campaigns leverage activities that engage communities, businesses, and policymakers in efforts to realize national and global sustainability goals collectively (Ajayi, 2020).

Public relations plays a very vital role in the area of advocacy and creating awareness in sustainable development. Through strategic communication, PR can educate the public on ways of living that are sustainable, protective of the environment, and socially responsible (Mefalopulos, 2008). In Nigeria, where issues of climate change, deforestation, and pollution are a threat to sustainable development, PR can influence behaviour change by promoting eco-friendly initiatives and encouraging corporate social responsibility (CSR) efforts (Ewah, 2019). Public relations campaigns can use a variety of vehicles - mass media, social media, and community engagement programs to create both awareness and action. Collaboration and stakeholder engagement are important components of sustainable development and, therefore, PR is that vehicle for forging strong partnerships.

Sustainable development goals (SDGs) can only be achieved if governments, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and the private sector work in tandem (Smith, 2021). Public relations strategies like stakeholder mapping, dialogue facilitation, and reputation management can help build trust and collaboration among various

actors (Lattimore et al., 2012). In Nigeria, effective PR can bridge the communication gap between the government agencies and the local communities, ensuring that development initiatives are in tandem with the needs and aspirations of the people.

Despite the potential of public relations in driving sustainable development, there are a number of challenges that clog the wheel of its effectiveness in Nigeria. Some of the barriers to achieving sustainability goals include inadequate access to communication infrastructure, misinformation, and inadequate public awareness (Akinwale, 2018). Moreover, the lack of trained PR professionals and inadequate funding for communication campaigns exacerbate these challenges. These barriers could only be surmounted by integrating public relations into the national development plans of action by the decision-makers and investing in capacity-building initiatives for PR practitioners. In this way, Nigeria can use strategic communication to advance sustainable development and enhance the quality of life for the people.

.Theoretical Review

Excellence Theory of Public Relations

This theory was advanced by James E. Grunig and David M. Dozier, 1984. Two-Way Symmetrical Communication: Effective public relations should create a mutual understanding and dialogue between the organizations and their publics, instead of persuading the people. Strategic Management Function: PR should be an integral part of the management process of an organisation in terms of its contribution towards decision making and ensuring that actions are within the public's interest. Organizational Culture: A participative organizational culture that values open communication with stakeholders supports the effectiveness of PR. Empowerment of PR Function: It is pertinent that the public relations department assumes an influential role in organizational decision-making for effective relation management with stakeholders. Ethical Responsibility: PR practices have to be guided by ethical principles of transparency, honesty, and respect in two-way communication. Building Long-Term Relationships: The focus should be on building and maintaining long-term, mutually beneficial relationships, not on short-term promotional tactics. Diversity and Inclusivity: Public relations should be effective in consideration and addressing the needs of diverse publics for inclusiveness and representation.

Assumptions of the Excellence Theory: Organisations that apply excellent public relations achieve better relationships with their publics, which in turn leads to organisational success and sustainability. Public relations should be proactive rather than reactive; therefore, it lays much emphasis on strategic planning and research in order to understand and serve the needs of stakeholders. Effective PR helps organisations to reduce organisational crises and conflicts because it allows open communication and transparency. Organisations that adopt two-way symmetrical communication enjoy increased trust, credibility, and stakeholder loyalty. PR works best when positioned at the decision-making level, operating in tandem with other organizational departments.

Criticism of the Excellence Theory: Two-way symmetrical communication is nearly an ideal in real life, as most organisations put their interests ahead of mutual benefits (Holtzhausen, 2002). The theory, therefore, probably does not give a completely accurate picture of the complex power relationships that exist between organisations

and their publics, which may all determine to a large extent the outcome of the communication efforts. It presumes that all stakeholders have equal access to the channels of communication, discounting the disparities in resources and technological access. Others believe that it overemphasises the strategic role of PR at the expense of its tactical and promotional aspects. Implementation of the excellence principles may be difficult in developing countries with meagre resources and bureaucratic constraints.

Significance to the Study: The Excellence Theory is very relevant to the study because it emphasizes strategic public relations in achieving effective governance and sustainable development in Nigeria. Ways through which symmetry in communication between the government and citizens can enhance public trust in and involvement of governance processes are opened up theoretically by its postulation. This research relates to the theoretical focus on ethical responsibility, strategic management, and inclusiveness in addressing governance issues arising from misinformation and lack of accountability to an assured wide public in Nigeria. With a relation from the previous point, the long-term relationship theoretical aspect brings out the idea of carrying out sustainable development with the help of effective PR strategies.

Empirical Review

Ogbondah (2017) researched "Public Relations and Governance in Nigeria: Bridging the Trust Deficit." The study explored the role of public relations in bridging the trust deficit between the Nigerian government and its citizens and how PR practices can help bring more transparency and accountability into governance. A qualitative method of research was adopted in which in-depth interviews were conducted with PR professionals, government officials, and citizens to obtain data concerning the perception of the public in government communication undertakings. The study found that ineffective communication strategies, a lack of transparency, and poor engagement with citizens are major causes for the distrust crisis facing the government of Nigeria. It indicated that public relations practices, such as two-way communication and transparent information sharing, were among the key solutions to bettering the quality of public trust toward the government. Both this study and the current study focus on how public relations can improve governance by enhancing transparency, accountability, and public trust. While the study under review was principally based on trust deficit in governance in relation to Nigeria, this underlines another perspective - sustainable development as a by-product of good public relations strategizing.

Ezeah (2020) conducted a study on "Crisis Communication Strategies in Nigeria's Public Sector". The study aimed at assessing the effectiveness of the crisis communication strategies adapted by the public institutions in Nigeria during the periods of crisis and its impact on the relation of people's trust and credibility toward the government. It combined a survey conducted with officials and citizens of the government with content analysis of the crisis communications produced by the public institutions. According to the study, effective and transparent communication during crises helped to ease negative public perception, while inadequate crisis communication strategies further fuelled distrust and confusion. In this regard, the use of media and social platforms was more effective in reaching a larger audience. Both the study and the current study explore how strategic communication,

especially public relations, can contribute positively toward government credibility and the public's trust in Nigeria. As the study reviewed focuses entirely on crisis communication, this one takes a more holistic approach to governance and sustainable development using PR strategies.

Ajayi (2020) researched "Strategic Public Relations for Sustainable Development in Africa." The study examined the role of public relations in promoting sustainable development in Africa, with a particular view toward how strategic PR may influence public policy and create awareness on social responsibility and environmental issues. A case study approach was adopted with a focus on PR campaigns in several African countries, including Nigeria. Interviews were held with PR professionals, and PR campaign documents were reviewed. The outcome showed that PR campaigns targeting the environment and social responsibility issues were effective in building awareness and stimulating public action toward sustainable practice. However, challenges of inadequate resources and political resistance were strong deterrents. While the reviewed study is based on environmental sustainability, both the current and reviewed study are based on sustainable development as an outcome of effective public relations strategies in governance. The reviewed study was more regionally focused on Africa with emphasis on environmental sustainability while the current study focuses on the broader role of PR in governance and development in Nigeria.

Gap Identification

Part of what is lacking from the literature review is the scant attention paid to the peculiar challenges that confront public relations in Nigerian governance, especially in terms of political interference, resource constraints, and inadequate professional training for PR practitioners. While existing literature has focused on the role of PR in ensuring transparency and public engagement, few studies have explored how these challenges impede the effective application of PR strategies in the Nigerian context. This gap highlights the need for more research on the practical challenges that impede the effective implementation of public relations in governance and how these could be overcome so as to secure better communication with, and enhancement of, public trust.

Methodology

This is a qualitative research design guided by the library research method, undertaken to examine the role of public relations in improving governance for the promotion of sustainable development in Nigeria. The population consisted of the aggregate total of academic literature, government reports, policy documents, books, and scholarly articles published, and reputable media sources that address the issues of public relations practices, governance challenges, and sustainable development initiatives in Nigeria. With such literature serving as the backdrop, the paper synthesized current, relevant theoretical and empirical findings related to the public relations aspect in governance and how communications can be deployed to ensure not just transparency but also accountability to see through sustainable developments. The library research method allows in-depth exploration into the secondary data covering much of the literature on this topic through numerous scholarly perspectives.

A purposive sampling method was adopted in selecting sources relevant to the study, which includes academic books, journal articles, government publications, and case studies that offer insights into public relations strategies

and their impact on governance in Nigeria. The total number of sources selected was 30-40, ensuring diversity and relevance to the study's focus. A systematic review of the selected literature was conducted to identify the key themes, patterns, and findings relating to the role of public relations in governance. Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data, where trends, repeated themes, and insights were identified. This helped establish relationships between existing works and understand how public relations could help improve governance and achieve sustainable development in Nigeria.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The themes were then deductively deduced from the research objectives. The following themes were deduced: Impact of Public Relations on Government Transparency and Accountability; Role of Public Relations in Public Engagement and Trust; and Challenges in Implementing Effective Public Relations for Governance. These are presented and discussed below:

Impact of Public Relations on Government Transparency and Accountability

The theme discusses how good public relations strategies impact levels of transparency and accountability within government operations in a way of earning citizens' trust and participation in governance. The public relations strategies are very important in increasing the transparency and accountability of the government through the creation of open and honest communication between the government institutions and the citizens. According to Grunig and Dozier (2002), two-way symmetrical communication, where feedback from the public is integrated into decision-making, is critical in making government policies and actions transparent. If the channels of communication are used properly, governments can use them to inform the citizens of their activities, clarify misconceptions, and provide periodic updates regarding the implementation of policies. The transparency is helpful in diffusing discontent among the public and at the same time gaining confidence in government institutions (Macnamara, 2016). Public relations strategies that would help to better enhance government credibility in the Nigerian context, where challenges of corruption and lack of accountability reign, are those with clear, consistent, and honest communication at the top of the list.

Moreover, public relations strategies involving stakeholder engagement are very instrumental in guaranteeing government accountability. Good PR enables governments to interact with not only the public but also other key stakeholders, such as the media, civil society organizations, and international bodies (Lattimore et al., 2012). In Nigeria, where citizens seem to be out of the decision-making loop, public relations strategies that allow for dialogue and participation by the public will go a long way to enhance accountability. For example, public consultations and town hall meetings, which are integral to good public relations practice, enable the government to pass information about their activities to the public and listen to the concerns of the latter, hence contributing to a more accountable governance structure (Ogbondah, 2017). Challenges of misinformation, political polarisation, and media manipulation may, however, be there to thwart effective PR strategies seeking to bring about transparency and accountability in Nigeria. As noted by Ezeah, 2020, fake news and one-sided reporting could distort government messages and destroy public confidence. While these challenges are rife, effective PR

campaigns that ensure accuracy, regularity, and inclusiveness of messaging can help dispel them. Public relations, through continued interactions with the citizens and putting them on the same page, is thus very important to enhance the government's transparency and accountability in Nigeria.

Role of Public Relations in Public Engagement and Trust

This theme researches the role that public relations plays in fostering public participation in government processes, building trust in government policies, and ensuring that citizens feel informed and involved. Public relations is at the centre in efforts to increase public engagement with and trust in government policies by acting as a bridge between government and citizens. Similarly, public relations practices founded on the basis of a two-way model of communication—that does not merely focus on getting information to the public but rather seeks the public's involvement in shaping policies are imperative in achieving high regard among people (Grunig & Hunt, 1984). Especially in societies characterized by Nigeria-type situations where skepticism towards authority seems normal, this could facilitate genuine engagement from ordinary people as full co-participants within policy dialogue with government policymakers. Such initiatives as public forums, media briefings, and social media engagement allow for the direct interaction of government officials and citizens in terms of transparency and participation (Kent & Taylor, 2016). This level of engagement creates a sense of ownership among the citizens in relation to the support they can offer to the initiatives of government.

Moreover, public relations campaigns in the area of trust-building may significantly improve the perception of government policies by the public. Public trust is based on the perception of government honesty, integrity, and competence (Macnamara, 2016). If good PR strategies are utilized, people are likely to have the feeling that their government is working for them and in their best interest. In a country like Nigeria, where scepticism towards government policies is normally high due to historical developments like corruption and mismanagement, an effective PR campaign structured with clarity would change public perception. For instance, clarity in communication about how the policies will benefit the citizens and clarity in explaining government actions can help in building confidence among its citizens (Ogbondah, 2017). However, in building trust, PR has to address the concerns of citizens and should be clear with facts.

According to Coombs (2019), a government that responds promptly to the queries and concerns of the public through PR efforts is likely to gain the trust of citizens. Given the tendency for misinformation and rumours to spread quickly in Nigeria, it is imperative that governments ensure PR efforts are proactive in addressing issues before they escalate. In this way, public relations not only enhances public engagement with government policies but also helps in establishing and maintaining long-term trust.

Challenges in Implementing Effective Public Relations for Governance

This theme explores the barriers and challenges that befall the implementation of public relations strategies within the Nigerian governance system, including issues to do with resources, infrastructure, and public perception. Challenges in using public relations effectively in Nigerian governance include political interference, lack of resources, and inadequate professional training. One of the major challenges is political interference, which in

most cases leads to biased or selective communication from the government agencies (Ajayi, 2020). If PR efforts are driven by political reasons, then credibility is lost, and as a result, the ability to bring about public trust and engagement becomes very minimal. Besides, the limitation of resources and funding for public relations campaigns limits government agencies' potential of communicating effectively with citizens. With the PR department being often so underfunded in Nigeria, practitioners sometimes do not have the tools and the platforms to reach the public at a larger scale (Ewah, 2019).

Another challenge faced is the provision of adequate training and capacity-building among PR practitioners in the public sector. Since most of those government officials responsible for public communication are not well trained in strategic communication, they often compromise the essence of implementing an effective PR practice (Lattimore et al., 2012). Most of the PR efforts in government fall short without the requisite experience in communication and media relations. Moreover, PR strategies may not be integrated into the decision-making process, which may lead to communication that is cut off from citizens' needs and expectations. Therefore, professional development programs and capacity-building initiatives are very important in enhancing the effectiveness of PR in Nigerian governance. The challenges will have to be addressed by the government of Nigeria investing in capacity-building initiatives for the PR professionals in the country, which will arm them with the necessary tools and training to engage the citizens.

Also, the government must ensure, on their part, that political involvement does not bias the public relations activities but rather it is based on transparency, accountability, and honesty (Grunig & Dozier, 2002). It is how Nigeria with these challenges will upgrade its public relation practices for effectiveness in governance, which will translate into sustainable development. Moreover, more resources need to be assigned to the PR function so that it is adequately resourced to support fully the various government initiatives and to engage meaningfully with the public.

Discussion of Findings

Findings showed that the public relations strategies, especially the two-way symmetrical model, contribute greatly towards government transparency and accountability since it facilitates effective dialogue between government institutions and the citizens, thereby allowing the citizens to trust the government more. The related study by Ogbondah (2017) on the role of public relations in bridging the trust deficit between the Nigerian government and citizens is relevant to the finding on transparency and accountability, as it highlights how effective PR strategies can improve government credibility through the enhancement of open communication and the reduction in mistrust. The focus on two-way symmetrical communication within the Excellence Theory directly relates to the finding that public relations strategies enhance government transparency and accountability, as it spots the role of mutual dialogue in the government-citizen relationship within the process of trust and assurance of transparent governance.

The findings have shown that public relations plays a vital role in increasing public engagement and trust in the policies of the government through clear and consistent communication and active involvement of citizens in the

decision-making process, hence creating a sense of participation and ownership. This can also be backed up by findings of Ezeah (2020), in which he discussed some crisis communication strategies in the public sector, outlining how open and responsive communication at times of crisis may be useful in bettering the perception of the public toward the government and earning trust via media and public relations initiatives. The focus of the Excellence Theory on strategic management and relationship building is applicable to the finding that public relations enhances public engagement and trust in government policies, as it flags how PR practices that involve stakeholders in decision-making foster greater citizen participation and trust in government actions. The Excellence Theory, through its tenet of empowering the public relations function within an organization, is applicable to the finding on challenges affecting PR in Nigerian governance, since it highlights professional training and adequate resources to enable the PR departments to cope with managing communication and bringing credibility to the government.

The findings of the study have identified the challenges that inhibit the effectiveness of public relations in Nigerian governance, including political interference, inadequate resources, and the lack of professional training for PR practitioners, which can be surmounted with capacity building and increased investment in communication tools and platforms. This was further demonstrated in the study by Ajayi (2020) on strategic public relations for sustainable development, which basically highlights the importance of overcoming the barriers of political interference and the lack of resources that are often related to ensuring that PR strategies work effectively within governance and in sustainable development. The Excellence Theory postulates that in order for a public relations function to be excellent within an organizational framework, professional training and armament with adequate resources by the PR department are necessary so that it succeeds in managing communications and building credibility for the government.

Combining the implications from the three findings, it reveals that the implementation of public relations strategies to enhance transparency and accountability would remarkably increase citizens' trust in government and lead toward a more participatory and inclusive political environment. This will also help the government to strengthen public relations efforts in effectively engaging citizens and increase public support for policies and actions of the government, hence bringing about cooperation and stability in society. Some of the challenges that can be surmounted in Nigerian governance include political interference, lack of resources, and inadequate professional training; these will result in effective communication and make PR a very important profession in helping to improve governance for sustainable development.

Conclusion

The study concluded that public relations strategies emphasizing two-way symmetrical communication are central to increasing transparency and accountability in governance, in that they bring about open, honest dialogue between government and citizens, thus engendering trust and credibility in governance.

The study explored that public relations plays a critical role in improving public engagement and trust in government policies through transparent, consistent, and inclusive communication that actively involves citizens, thereby enhancing their sense of participation and support for government actions.

Finally, the study has pointed out that the greatest challenges that public relations faces in Nigerian governance, characterized by political interference, resource constraints, and a lack of professional training for effective communication, can only be resolved through the building up of capacities and further investment in the infrastructure of PR to ensure the attainment of sustainable development goals.

This goes a long way in adding to the knowledge on how public relations can enhance governance in Nigeria through increased transparency, accountability, and public trust. The findings indicate that effective public relations, especially two-way communication and stakeholder engagement strategies, are important in bridging the trust gap between the government and citizens to foster an all-inclusive and participatory political environment. With valuable insight into how strategic communication practices can extend the credibility of these government institutions, this study makes it possible to view more clearly how public relations can be applied in a way that will help address governance challenges and make policies emanating from the government more accessible and transparent to the people.

It also identifies those specific challenges that are in the way of effective public relations in governance in Nigeria: political interference, lack of resources, and inadequate training of PR professionals. Identification of these barriers provides very important recommendations on how to improve the capacity of public Relations in the Public Sector. Such contribution extends the existing corpus of knowledge and provides workable solutions to surmount these challenges, thus enabling public relations practitioners to contribute meaningfully to sustainable development and to enhance the overall efficacy of governance in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the work, the following are the recommendations that have been made.

1. The Nigerian government public relations practice should adapt two-way communication-based strategies, ensuring transparency and accountability with a constant interaction level between government institutions and citizens.
- 2) Enhance public relations efforts that will enable greater public involvement and trust in government policies through increased transparency in communication and participation of citizens in the decision-making process.
3. The Nigerian government should address challenges facing public relations in governance through the provision of adequate resources and training for PR professionals, ensuring that communication efforts are free from political interference.

References

- Adegbola, O. (2021). The impact of digital media on public relations practice in Nigeria. *African Journal of Communication*, 8(1), 45-60.

- Ajayi, O. (2020). *Strategic public relations for sustainable development in Africa*. Spectrum Books.
- Akintola, O. I., Omipidan, I., & Ifeduba, E. (2023). A literature review of public relations research in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research*, 6(3). <https://ijssmr.org/vol-6-issue-3/a-literature-review-of-public-relations-research-in-nigeria/>
- Akinwale, A. (2018). Communication challenges in achieving sustainable development goals in Nigeria. *Journal of Development Communication*, 29(2), 112-130.
- Aribisala, T. M., Samson, A., & Chinenye, N. P. (2023). Impact of digital public relations on good governance, accountability, and national integration in Nigeria. *Path of Science*, 9(8), 5009-5019.
- Coombs, W. T. (2019). *Ongoing crisis communication: Planning, managing, and responding*. Sage Publications.
- Cutlip, S. M., Center, A. H., & Broom, G. M. (2013). *Effective public relations*. Pearson Education.
- Egwuonwu, T. K., Kabuoh, M. N., & Ajike, E. O. (2015). Imperatives of public relations strategies and Nigeria vision 20:20:20 development goals. *International Policy Brief Series*, 10(5). <https://internationalpolicybrief.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/ARTICLE-10-5.pdf>
- Ewah, E. (2019). *Corporate social responsibility and environmental sustainability in Nigeria*. Lagos Malthouse Press.
- Ezeah, G. (2020). Crisis communication strategies in Nigeria's public sector. *Nigerian Journal of Communication*, 17(1), 23-39.
- Grunig, J. E., & Dozier, D. M. (1984). *Managing public relations*. Holt, Rinehart & Winston.
- Grunig, J. E., & Dozier, D. M. (2002). *Excellent public relations and effective organizations*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Grunig, J. E., & Hunt, T. (1984). *Managing public relations*. Holt, Rinehart, and Winston.
- Holtzhausen, D. R. (2002). Resistance from the margins: the postmodern public relations practitioner as organizational activist. *Journal of Public Relations Research*, 14(1), 57-84.
- Kent, M. L., & Taylor, M. (2016). From dialogue to engagement: Toward an inclusive public relations paradigm. *Public Relations Journal*, 10(1), 1-17.

- Lattimore, D., Baskin, O., Heiman, S. T., & Toth, E. L. (2012). *Public relations: The profession and the practice*. McGraw-Hill.
- Macnamara, J. (2016). *Organizational listening: The missing essential in public communication*. Peter Lang.
- Mefalopulos, P. (2008). *Development communication sourcebook: Broadening the boundaries of communication*. World Bank.
- Nwosu, I. E. (1990). Public relations in the Nigerian government system. *Nigerian Journal of Public Affairs*, 10(1), 45-60.
- Ogbondah, C. (2017). Public relations and governance in Nigeria: Bridging the trust deficit. *African Journal of Political Science*, 11(2), 78-91.
- Otuya-Asohro, E. O. (2024). Harnessing the potentials of tourism in Nigeria through public relations. *Journal of Tourism and Heritage Studies*, 3(1).
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329545595_Public_Relations_Strategies_and_Tourism_Development_in_Nigeria.
- Smith, R. D. (2021). *Strategic planning for public relations*. Routledge.
- United Nations. (1987). *Our common future*. Oxford University Press.